

THE MESSAGE IS THE AGENT: NEXUS AND SEMIOSPHERE IN SOCIAL MEDIA COMMUNICATION

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Abstract

The rising global importance of social network sites (SNS) transforms them into a relevant new theatre for negotiating and constructing perceptions of reality. Aiming to bridge the material-semiotic divide, this study harkens back to Lotman's semiosphere theory and Gell's theory of the art nexus to throw light on fundamental mechanisms of SNS interaction involving human and non-human actors, and communities holding different norms, perceptions, and presuppositions. It asks: How are messages and meanings created, shared and translated in communication involving diverse points of view on social network sites? How does semiotic agency circulate between human and non-human entities (messages, their authors and readers, other affected bodies, as well as underlying norms, perceptions and presuppositions) involved in SNS communication? How could communication on social network sites be formally represented to account well for processes of semiotic translation and distribution of agency between human and non-human actors in actual SNS interactions? To address these questions, it uses as case study an SNS conversation on the removal of a public monument to a controversial author of the Soviet period in contemporary Lithuania. It applies the Connective ontology, a formal conceptual domain model of SNS communication, to represent interactions between users in this conversation as a process of semiotic translation involving opposing semiospheres with very different assumptions of what is real, what is important, and what is right. It illustrates how key ontology entities can serve to represent the circulation of meanings in an SNS conversation and the role of semiospheres in blocking interpretations and catalysing meaning-making. Following Gell, it elaborates a conceptualisation of SNS

interactions as communicative nexus, involving Authors, Indexes, Prototypes and Recipients in binary relationships where semiotic agency circulates between them in a process of recursive abduction, demonstrating how agents of meaning involve not just human but also non-human actors in situated contexts of SNS interaction that are affected by and have implications across a blended, virtual-physical reality.

Keywords

Social network sites, Alfred Gell, Yuri Lotman, semiosphere, nexus theory

Introduction

Digital information technologies (IT) developed at the end of the 20th century cause significant changes in the economic, political, and cultural processes and the development of society in general. On a global scale, they contribute to the formation of the Network Society and the emergence of associated socio-cultural effects (Castells 1997; Dijk 2005), including the increased significance of blended digital culture as a kind of interaction between digital technology, physical reality, and the people. As we consider the terms of this interaction in the context of digital culture, we do not consider the relationship between “virtual” (digital) and physical (non-digital) as an opposition between “false” and “real” worlds. Instead, we perceive them as distinct in terms of their technologies and media (for example, the digital world is discrete and the physical world as continuous) yet at the same time entangled as elements of an integrative, blended reality.

Social networking spanning across such a blended (virtual and physical) reality plays a key role in the Network Society (Dijk 2006) and in the development of digital culture (Miller 2020). The rising global importance of social network site (SNS) platforms transforms them into a relevant new theatre for negotiating and constructing perceptions of reality. A quantitative analysis of Web of Science Core Collection (1990-present) found a dizzying number of 119,319 articles related to social networks (as topic), but, among these, over 63% are works within computer science and engineering (information systems, theory and methods, artificial intelligence, telecommunications, and interdisciplinary applications) predominate. Conversely, only ca. 4% of such studies address social

networks from the perspective of communication studies; of these, many concern definitional and early stage overviews and conceptualisation (e.g., Boyd & Ellison 2007); studies related to social capital (e.g., Ellison et al. 2007; Valenzuela 2009; Zuniga 2012); consumer engagement (e.g., Chu & Kim 2011); risks of social media (e.g., Livingstone 2008), homophily bubbles and echo chambers (e.g., Flaxman et al. 2016), and, within works in the last five years (2018-22), also studies related to the COVID-19 pandemic (e.g., Smith & Graham 2019; Salavera et al. 2020), to social media use by older adults (e.g., Hunsaker & Hargittai 2018), to emotion (e.g., Waterloo et al. 2018), and privacy (e.g., Obar & Oeldorf-Hirsch 2020).

A key realisation arising from these studies is that SNS communication often involves interaction between different collectivities and points of view, and that it also becomes a theatre for distribution of agency between human actors and non-human entities by way of communication. While the vast literature in the field addresses consequential higher-level aspects of communication and social action on social networks, there is still a gap in understanding the working mechanisms of semiosis on social networks, related to the construction (encoding), dissemination, and reading (decoding) of messages at the most fundamental level. In response to this situation, our research aims to understand better:

RQ1: How are messages and meanings created, shared and translated in communication involving diverse points of view on social network sites?

RQ2: How does semiotic agency circulate between human and non-human entities (messages, their authors and readers, other affected bodies, as well as underlying norms, perceptions and presuppositions) involved in SNS communication?

RQ3: How could communication on social network sites be formally represented to account well for processes of semiotic translation and distribution of agency between human and non-human actors in actual SNS interactions?

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Theoretical perspectives: semiosphere and the art nexus

In this study, we draw key concepts for understanding the process and structure of conversations on SNS from two theoretical frameworks: semiosphere theory, originally developed by Yuri Lotman (1922–1993), the leading figure of the school of cultural semiotics associated with the University of Tartu, Estonia (Lotman 1990; Lotman 2005), and the theory of the art nexus, developed within the agentive anthropology of material culture of Alfred Gell (1998). By combining the notions of semiosphere and art nexus, we seek to capture semiotic dimensions of SNS conversations, analysing this phenomenon in the context of communication studies, while also accounting for the distribution of agency between human and non-human actors, and thus bridging the material-semiotic divide and the separation between communication and social action.

Lotman defines the semiosphere as a spatial mechanism the primary functions of which are to communicate existing information, generate new information, and preserve information. In this sense, the semiosphere may be conceived as a global semiotic system that integrates all possible signs, texts, interpretations, symbols, information, knowledge, representations and their relationships, including their interaction with the non-semiotic elements from outside of the semiosphere (and functioning, thus, as an open system). The emergence of the concept of the semiosphere was prompted by the understanding that the starting point of any communication system is not a separate and isolated sign, but a semiotic space (i.e., a semiosphere) which affords a communication interface between at least two signs (Lotman 2005). Each semiosphere, according to Lotman, consists of a centre and peripheries. From an epistemic point of view, the centre may be defined by dominant semiotic structures (ideas, narratives, theories or metaphors) typical for a particular community within a given period. The periphery of the semiosphere is not meant as an ideas dump. It is, rather, a space of creolisation: a term creolisation used by Lotman to denote the process of deep intersection between two semiospheres. Creolised space emerges as the new intercultural (or inter-semiospheric) space generated by the semiotic structures of the intersecting semiospheres. This space is understandable and recognisable for members of both semiospheres, and is the site of the most intensive inter-semiospheric relationships and dialogue between them. It is in this space where new semiotic structures are created, usually through dialogue and interaction between members of both communities. These new semiotic structures, created in the creolised periphery, may transmute

into a newly-formed centre and thus become dominant in a particular semiosphere in the future (Lotman 2019).

Alfred Gell, on the other hand, offers a re-conceptualisation of material culture which, drawing from his earlier anthropological work and from his engagement with Peircean semeiotic theory, proposes an alternative theorisation of how “art objects” (i.e., material artefacts) function in cultural contexts not merely as communicative signs, but crucially also as things ripe with *agency*, shifting focus from what objects ‘mean’ to what objects ‘do’ (Gell 1998). In Gell’s approach, objects become *efficacious* as (secondary) social agents by virtue of “a certain technically achieved level of excellence” (Gell 1996, 43) imbuing the technical mastery and (primary) agency of their creator. Material culture thus becomes a *technology of enchantment*, as agency is distributed from a maker (as *agent*) to a material thing and to those affected by that material thing or, more generally, between human or non-human *agents*, *indexes*, and *patients*. Gell’s approach signals a shift from object to process: “The power of ... objects stems from the technical processes they objectively embody: the *technology of enchantment* is founded on the *enchantment of technology*” (Gell 1996, 44). It also calls for a fundamental re-thinking of the notion of identity: through their entanglement with objects, humans establish identity through what Gell calls “distributed personhood”, an “extended self” that involves, for example, the weapon of a soldier as a constitutive part of his identity; and objects, such as one’s car, can be conceived as humans, or have “physiognomies like people” (Gell 1998, 15).

In his last, posthumously published monograph (1998), Gell draws from the Peircean semeiotic to develop fully his theory of the *art nexus*, precisely in order to provide a systematics of his broader theorisation of material culture. The key notion in his theory is the *abduction of agency*: objects function as *indexes* (in the sense of Peirce’s “firstness”) to distribute agency - the power to act - involving human subjects and non-human objects, and this is a fundamental dimension to social practice. The art nexus is defined as a relational structure involving four terms, the *index*, the *artist*, the *recipient*, and the *prototype*, which assume relations of *agent* and *patient* in different combinations between them. In the context of Gell’s theory, the index is defined as “...the visible, physical, ‘thing’ [which] permits ... the abduction of agency”; the *artist* is the one to whom “...the authorship of the index (as a physical thing) is attributed”; the recipients are those “in relation to whom, by abduction, indexes are considered to exert agency, or who exert agency via the index”, for

instance, an art patron who acquires fame through an artwork produced by an artist under his patronage; and finally, the prototype is “the entity which the index represents visually (as an icon, depiction, etc.) or non-visually”, as in the example of a deity being represented by a rock (Gell 1998, 16-27).

Memory conflicts on SNS: removing Petras Cvirka’s monument

Petras Cvirka (1909-1947) became a controversial figure in the history of 20th-century Lithuania. On one hand, he was a well-known writer whose works were included in the school literature curriculum during the Soviet period, but at the same time he held political positions in the Soviet administration, wrote articles glorifying the Red Army, the Soviet Union and Joseph Stalin, and took part in the Moscow delegation that “asked” for the incorporation of Lithuania into the Soviet Union in 1940. In 1959, a monument to Petras Cvirka was erected in Vilnius. Although many Soviet period monuments were removed after Lithuania regained its independence in 1990, Cvirka’s statue was preserved at that time. The public narrative of Petras Cvirka was structured into two parts, separating his political and creative activities, and public communication emphasised the creative activities of Petras Cvirka, while downplaying the political ones. However, when Russia started to reanimate the idea of the Soviet Union (e.g., in Vladimir Putin’s annual state address in 2005 denigrating the collapse of the Soviet Union as “the greatest geopolitical catastrophe of the century”), the debate on Soviet monuments in Lithuania started again, and intensified after Russia’s annexation of Crimea in 2014. The monument to Petras Cvirka in Vilnius became one of the targets of this debate as attention shifted to his political, pro-Soviet activities, and in September 2021 the Vilnius City Council eventually decided to remove the monument. The operation was carried out in November of the same year.

In the “Connective Digital Memory in the Borderlands” project, a transdisciplinary team of researchers has been investigating how heritage and memories of the difficult past shape SNS communication on contemporary identities and attitudes in Lithuania. From a corpus of 3,061 conversations (threads consisting of a post optionally followed by comments and replies to comments) in the Lithuanian language, the project identified 33 conversations referring to Petras Cvirka, posted between July 2018 and December 2021, most of which debate the removal

of the statue. An conversation initiated by a post at the Delfi news network's page (<https://www.facebook.com/DelfiLietuva/posts/5581889748506709>) can serve as an useful case of communicative activity on SNS for the present study (Fig.1).

Figure 1. Facebook conversation on the removal of Petras Cvirka's monument, 18 November 2018 (first page screenshot).

The post merely links to an online article, posted on 18 November 2021, entitled “Monument to Petras Cvirka will be moved on Friday”, which reports on the City Council's plans for moving the statue to the collection of the National Museum of Lithuania, and mentions the long-term controversy and opposing views about the fate of the monument and the fact that it had been removed from the government's official list of protected monuments a few months before. Quoting Vilnius Vice Mayor

Valdas Benkunskas, the article notes that the decision for removal was based on “the explanation provided two years ago by the Lithuanian Genocide and Resistance Research Center that P. Cvirka collaborated with the Soviet authorities and contributed to the repression of other writers of that time”. A video of the removal was added to the article after 19 November 2021. The post itself includes a photograph of the upper part of the statue, dramatically shot from below.

Reactions to the post were divided, consisting of 167 “like”, 92 “angry”, 88 “sad”, 31 “wow”, 29 “love”, four “haha” and one “care” emoticon. Within just a three-day period from 18 November to 21 November 2021, the conversation elicited 320 comments (including replies), many of which attracted emoticon reactions too. Comments and replies address the removal of the monument from different perspectives. Supporters suggest that the statue is rightly removed as it celebrates someone who benefited from the Soviet occupation, a “bloody collaborator”, a “traitor”, “a complete minion of the Soviet government” who, according to the Lithuanian Resistance and Genocide Centre, as they mention, “obviously acted against the Lithuanian nation by betraying writers who worked underground”. Several people bring up the recognition of Cvirka by the Soviet establishment, and the fact that he was part of a delegation which brought to Vilnius “Stalin’s sun”, a monument recognized as a symbol of Soviet occupation. Opponents argue that the “history of Lithuania is being destroyed”, that the statue “does not bother anyone”, that it belongs to “our history, good or bad”, even exclaiming “what a pity [that] we try to erase our past”. Some suggest that politics stay out of memorialisation, and that Cvirka should be assessed on his value as a poet and not on his political affiliation, but others disagree. One user states: “[t]he destroyers of Lithuanian history will erect some iron four-legged cone instead of the writer and will call it art to make our children and grandchildren degenerates”; along similar lines, others deplore the possibility that the statue will be replaced by some contemporary art sculpture incomprehensible to them: “another Vilnius pipe” or “loads of scrap metal [like] on the Green Bridge” (a Soviet era monument in Vilnius that had been replaced recently by a contemporary art sculpture).

The conversation sometimes veers on more general questions, such as who else in public life may have been complicit to Soviet crimes, how many Lithuanians supported the Soviet annexation, to what extent should negative or dark memories be preserved or forgotten. Going beyond, they also sometimes make identity statements such as: “I am one who will never support crimes against humanity and an individual - neither Bolshevik reds nor fascists”. But some interactions become personal, even

abusive, as when one opponent to the decision suggests that Vilnius mayor Remigijus “Šimašius will be replaced with scrap metal”, while another calls removal of statue supporters “Šimašius’ whores”. “Are you a fan of Stalin’s sun bearers?”, a woman supporter counteracts, implying that opposers condone Cvirka’s collaboration with the Soviet regime. A man admonishes another: “Use arguments and not Soviet emotion, you flabby belly vatnik” (a slang term meaning Russian nationalist simpleton), only to be berated: “in your account [you are] looking at women’s clothes, do whatever you want”. When one user tells another “you don’t want to know the real story, apparently you like it distorted, fanciful”, the second user blocks her, adding “you’re mad [because] you can’t see my posts and personal pictures”. Conversations are ripe with presupposition and allusion, while irony or sarcasm is often used, as when a user suggests: “We should build sculptures of gravels, birds and pets [rather than of notable people]. This will suit all governments and all eras”. Hyperbole is also at play, for example when another user asks: “When will they start burning the books?”. Occasionally, memes are used to press a point: a clip of Leonardo di Caprio clapping with the word “Bravo!” in overlay (from “The wolf of Wall Street”), apparently in approval of the decision to remove the statue, while a suggestion that “if we remove everything from Lithuanian history like this, there will soon be no such textbook” frames a short clip with a smiling baby pointing a finger at the camera, in apparent opposition to the decision.

This conversation provides a vivid example on how things such as the Cvirka monument, when becoming the focus of social interaction in a communicative setting such as Facebook, can reinforce collective bonds linking individuals together in groups based on shared perceptions and feelings. The “affiliative power of objects” originally demonstrated by Lucy Suchman with regard to the multiple affiliations of a 8200 Xerox photocopier as both a mundane instrument of office practice, an engineering artefact and a scientific object of research (Suchman 2005), and later with regard to how Greek users interact with Facebook posts of museum artefacts – a photo of the 1922 refugee crisis tents in front of the Theseion temple in the Athenian Agora, the missing Caryatid in the Acropolis museum, or a photo of Athens at the break of the Greek Civil War (Dallas 2018) - is also enacted by Svirka’s monument, through the different ways it is conceived and represented in this Facebook conversation shaping the ties between supporters and opposers of its removal and their collective identities. Rhetorical and pragmatic discourse devices such as allusion, presupposition, and wordplay (Wodak 2007) are

instrumental for the construction of the conversation, and participants expend notable effort in seeking to align or negotiate their differing existential presuppositions on the historical past, and dissonant assumptions about the meaning of notions such as heritage, historical memory, and freedom. User interactions are dialogic, with people engaging in quasi-synchronous conversation which in our example has an agonistic (Mouffe 1999) rather than deliberative character - in other words, they fight over opposing points of view rather than building a cooperative argument - typically with only one or two users at a time. Participants in the conversation may be assigned to larger groups with different perceptions of the issues discussed, but as a rule interact across groups. They do not merely exchange ideas and information, but have stakes that relate to their values, identity and heritage, and are emotionally invested in specific objects, issues and positions.

Modeling SNS conversations as semiotic activities

Conceptual models, understood as proto-theories suitable for elucidation and validation (Bates 2005), have been found to be useful for the definition of the main entities and relationships that capture salient aspects of a domain of inquiry, i.e., its ontology (Crotty 1998). Models range from rough schematisations to domain ontologies, defined as formal specifications of shared conceptualisations of a domain (Guarino et al. 2009). Most relevant to the subject of the current study, in the context of the “Connective Digital Memory in the Borderlands Project” we developed a domain ontology aimed specifically at representing semiotic and activity-centred aspects of heritage-related communication on social network sites (Kirtiklis et al. forthcoming). The Connective ontology draws from cultural-historical activity theory to account for the event-centric dimension of SNS interaction, adopting as its foundation the widely accepted CIDOC CRM ontology of cultural information, also known as ISO standard 21127 for the integration, mediation, and interchange of heterogeneous cultural heritage information (Bekiari et al. 2021), while integrating concepts derived from semiosphere theory to account for semiotic dimensions of SNS communication. Aimed as a pragmatic tool for the “systematic, evidence-based representation and study of referential and discursive aspects of conversations on HMI on SNS, of interviews with participants in such conversations, and of scholarly works engaging with such phenomena”, the Connective ontology focuses particularly in representing adequately the “the relationship

between Expressions and Meanings expressed by Persons and shared with Collectivities whose communicative practice as governed by specific Semiotic Codes” in SNS communication (Kirtiklis et al. forthcoming). A simplified diagrammatic representation presents the main entities and relationships of the Connective ontology of semiotic activity on SNS (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Core ontology of semiotic activity on SNS: semiosis and agency aspects (amended from Kirtiklis et al. forthcoming, Fig. 1).

Its central entity is *Semiotic Activity*, a kind of *Activity* that represents those SNS activities that are communicative or meaning-laden. Walking through the entities and relationships in the diagram, each Semiotic Activity may consist of multiple more granular Semiotic Activities; therefore, it may represent something as broad as someone’s overall communicative history on Facebook, or as granular as a single reaction to a specific Facebook comment. In addition, a Semiotic Activity may be continued by another Semiotic Activity, as when writing a Facebook post is followed by writing a comment on the post. A Semiotic Activity may

use a specific system *Affordance or Tool*, i.e. some system functionality; an Affordance or Tool may have more granular Affordances or Tools as components, and thus may represent from the entire set of functionalities of a social media platform such as Facebook to the minimal affordance of providing a “like” button in the same platform.

Any Semiotic Activity is carried out by some *Person* and may involve one or more instances of some *Collectivity*: for example, a Semiotic Activity may be said to be addressed to a Collectivity when posting a comment on the timeline of a Facebook group. A Person may belong to one or more Collectivities; for example, a SNS user may be a member of multiple Facebook groups, but also of non-digital social and cultural formations, communities, organisations, etc. A Person may assert, and a Person or Collectivity may have a particular value of belief in or affect for, some *Meaning*, which can be a proposition, question, evaluation, sentiment, motivation, etc. Also, a Collectivity may have competence in some *Semiotic Code*, an entity that refers to a set of shared expressions, vocabulary and rules enabling human communication; as Persons can be members of more than one Collectivities, it follows that they may have competence in multiple Semiotic Codes.

A Semiotic Activity produces or modifies some *Expression*, representing some document, linguistic or visual object with a recognizable form which acts as a carrier of meaning. An Expression can have as component other Expressions: it can be as broad as a full Facebook conversation thread including comments and media, and as narrow as a word, a link or a photograph embedded in a post. Expression may have some language if it consists of text. Each Expression refers to, is about or represents one or more instances of Meaning. An Expression may also refer to, be about, or represent any *Referent*, the most general entity in the ontology, which subsumes as sub-classes all other entities; in other words, all instances of Activity, Tool or Affordance, Person, Collectivity, Semiotic Code, Expression, Meaning or Concept are also Referents. For instance, a Facebook post may refer to one or more historical events, actions, places, material objects, etc. In addition, a Semiotic Activity may be influenced or motivated by some Meaning; for example, ‘posting a comment in a commemorative Facebook group’ may be motivated by ‘feeling nostalgic’ (an instance of Meaning) or influenced by a Meaning which a previous post on the same Facebook thread (an instance of Expression) refers to or is about.

Finally, the Concept entity accounts for characterizations or notions which do not require the definition of additional properties; each Concept may have as a broader term some other Concept or define typical parts of some

other Concept. Subclasses of Referent such as Semiotic Activity, Expression, Collectivity, Meaning, Affordance or Tool, etc. may have as type some instance from a relevant sub-hierarchy of Concept. For example, an instance of Semiotic Activity such as ‘retweeting’ a tweet has type ‘disseminating’, an instance of Concept within a sub-hierarchy restricted to the characterization of Activities; on the other hand, the Expression “#idlenomore’ has type ‘hashtag’”, an instance of Concept in a sub-hierarchy identifying different formats and genres of Expression. In CIDOC CRM terminology, the relationship “Referent has type Concept” is a shortcut (Bekiari et al. 2021, 21), standing in place of an Activity of classification of the Referent as a Concept. The relationship between an Expression and its Meaning, the connection between a Person and some Collectivity, the belief some Person or Collectivity has in some Meaning, and the competence of a Collectivity in a Semiotic Code are also shortcuts. The model may be applicable to a range of semiotic activities on social media communities, to scholarly work related to such activities, and to interactions between them. Such interactions may be seen as understood as processes of retroduction, involved in the production of knowledge when researchers re-express the terms of some reality in theoretical terms (Bhaskar 1979). In the broader context of semiotic activity and digital curation “in the wild” (Dallas 2016), such processes correspond closely to the notion of translation, occurring in the boundaries between non-professional and professional semiospheres engaged in cultural HMI practices (Laužikas et al. 2018).

Looking holistically at the structure of the model, we recognise an interesting pattern. Relationships in the bottom part of the diagram, connecting Semiotic Activity with Semiotic Code, Expression, Referent, Concept and Meaning address the communicative aspect of semiosis that is the purview of semiosphere theory; more directly, the relationship “a Collectivity has competence in some Semiotic Code”, and its constituent entities are co-extensional with central dimensions of the notion of semiosphere. On the other hand, relationships in the top part of the diagram, connecting Semiotic Activity with notions of Affordance or Tool, Semiotic Code, Collectivity, Person and Meaning relate to the socio-material aspect of agency, addressed by Gell’s anthropological theory of the art nexus; but the concept of the art nexus, encapsulating all possible distributions of agency between pairs of index, subject, recipient and prototype assuming roles of agent and patient, appears to correspond not to any specific part but to the entire model. In what follows, to turn to these two aspects, examining in turn how a model of semiotic activity on SNS

may account for the translation of meanings between intersecting semiospheres, and how it can also account for the distribution of agency between human subjects and semiotic entities involved in SNS activity.

Semiotic translation: circulation of meaning between semiospheres on SNS

Applying Lotman's semiosphere theory to analyse communication in blended social networks enables us to interpret SNS conversations as the result of interaction between two semiospheres, and conceptualise the communication process as a kind of semiotic translation. In the context of Lotman's theory, communicative entities on SNS (such as message texts, photographs, videos, hyperlinks, etc.) are composed of signs, which are combined into text, conceived as an orderly sign system arranged for communication, and thus distinguishable from other kinds of systems. The articulation of elementary signs into text is governed by semiotic rules, providing the conditions for interpretation by individual conversation participants. Thus interpretations are 'individual', 'personal', and 'unique', in certain senses, but they are driven by existing community knowledge – particular schemas representing syllogisms typical and intelligible for a particular community (understood as semiosphere). These schemas work as frames for the meaning-making process by: (i) filtering and rejecting foreign communicative objects and meanings (coming from outside, in interaction with other semiospheres) which are unacceptable to the insider community (as semiosphere), and (ii) interpreting filtered communicative objects and assigning meanings to create text understandable to other insider community members. Such features enable us to identify these organising structures as 'framing schemas', or narratives, which act as tools connecting individual interpretation with community knowledge.

The existence of communicative objects and community knowledge catalyse SMS conversations – the emergence of new signs, and new texts intended for members of different communities of interest. Technically, this process consists in the translation of meanings from one semiosphere to another. In this, participants in SNS conversation become translators and interpreters, reading the texts and interpreting signs communicated by another SNS participant. In tandem, the translating participant mobilises existing community knowledge and catalyses the emergence of new community knowledge. This knowledge produces new texts, created using

a semiotic code understandable for members of the translating participant's community.

This process of translation could also be conceptualised as a manifestation of creolisation at the intersecting boundaries between two different communities (conceived as semiospheres). In this creolisation space, a text created in the 'language' (semiotic code) of one community is translated into a target 'language', enabling members of the target community to engage in efficacious (re-)use of communicative objects within their "own" community. This process is conditioned by the needs, motives, goals and aspirations of the target community, e.g., for learning, identity formation, social capital, entertainment, or creativity.

Aspects of this elaboration of semiosphere theory in the context of SNS communication can be mapped to constructs and operations in the Connective ontology of SNS semiotic activity. In analogy with Vernadsky's originating concept of biosphere, Lotman's semiosphere may be understood in a spatiotemporal sense - as a "place" - but also as the total sum of "semiotic organisms" inhabiting that place. While Lotman also conceives of *the* semiosphere in a universal sense of the whole domain where semiosis occurs, his most relevant sense in our context is the enumerative one, whereby human communicative actions are situated within *different* semiospheres, enabling practices of creolization at the (potential) boundary areas where these semiospheres intersect. Therefore, in the SNS communication context, we may more fruitfully conceive multiple communities sharing a common semiotic code and way of communication, as well as common beliefs, affects and attitudes, as potentially intersecting semiospheres. In our ontology, the notion of semiosphere is therefore best represented not as a perdurant single entity, but as a knowledge graph involving Persons belonging to a Collectivity able to communicate in a given Semiotic code, engaging in specific Semiotic Activities which produce or consume a great variety of possible Expressions, and sharing particular beliefs and/or affects towards a finite repertoire of Meanings. Identifying the significant properties of a particular semiosphere, therefore, can be served by building repertoires and accounting for relationships across these entities.

The notion of sign is represented in the ontology by adopting a standard Saussurean distinction between *signifier*, represented by the Expression entity, and *signified*, represented by Meaning. True to an activity-centred orientation, the ontology does recognise that a *sign*, represented as a relationship between an Expression and its Meaning(s), is not a binary mapping but it is a "shortcut" (Bekiari et al. 2021) for a Semiotic Activity

in its own right, in other words it constitutes a sign function involving a semiotic process of encoding-decoding (Hall 1980). Expanding this shortcut produces a knowledge graph that can account more explicitly for the process of creolisation and semiotic translation as conceived by semiosphere theory (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. Knowledge graph of a process of semiotic translation across two intersecting semiospheres.

The process represented involves a single Expression, which mediates between two Semiotic Activities: (a) an activity of posting (Semiotic activity: encoding/posting) on social media by an author (Person: author) who belongs to an originating community (Collectivity: author’s community) able to communicate in a given code (Semiotic code: author community ‘language’) sharing certain beliefs and affects (Meaning: author/community beliefs and affects), producing an message (Expression: SNS post) and imbuing it with a certain meaning for the author (Meaning: author’s meaning), and (b) an activity of reading (Semiotic activity: decoding/reading) by a reader (Person: reader) who belongs to a target community (Collectivity: reader’s community) able to communicate in a different code (Semiotic code: reader community ‘language’) sharing a different set of beliefs and affects (Meaning: reader community beliefs and affects), consuming the very same message (Expression: SNS post) but imbuing it with a new set of meanings for the *reader* (Meaning: reader’s

meaning), affected by both the author's set of meanings assigned to the Expression (Meaning: for author) and the presuppositions, norms, emotions of the reader and the reader community (Meaning: reader/community beliefs & affects).

The process of translation lies in the core of user interactions in the Svirka monument conversation on Facebook. The Delfi.lt article linked in the initial post (the Expression), merely communicated on the imminent plans (the main author's Meaning) of removing the monument (one of several Referents of the Expression), quoting the justification offered by the vice-mayor without taking a position on whether the decision was right or wrong. Multiple users (Persons) established different interpretations of the post (the readers' Meaning) drawing from dissonant presuppositions, normative views, and affects endorsed by different groups (reader Collectivities) with which they affiliated: supporters of the removal seem to adopt a coherent reading, translating the meaning of the removal of the statue as an act of transitional justice against a collaborator of an occupying foreign power. Opponents of the removal, on the other hand, seem to be divided between markedly different semiospheres underlying different meaning translations: some interpreting the removal as an unnecessary invasion of politics in considerations related to art and cultural memory, others as a sign of cultural decadence and abandonment of traditional values, while others still as an illiberal erasure of a period which, while troubled, should still be considered as part of Lithuanian history and collective heritage.

Abduction of semiotic agency: SNS interaction as communicative nexus

In terms of Alfred Gell's art nexus theory, "art objects are the equivalent of persons, or more precisely, social agents." (Gell 1998). Reframing SNS conversations in the context of the theory of the art nexus makes it possible to conceptualize how a semiotic object in SNS communication, operating as an index, acquires capabilities to produce effects separate from the intent and semiotic activity of its creator. To apply the theory, it is necessary to consider the process of abduction of agency between index, artist, prototype and recipient as they take positions of agent and patient in Gell's original context of material culture and anthropological art and map it to the context of communication on social media. In an approach analogous to reconceptualising the art nexus as "food nexus" to analyse

the cultural practice of Mexican gastronomy (Adapon 2008) and, closer to the focus of the present study, to the application of Gell's theory to investigate practices of blogging (Reed 2005) and digital storytelling (Westman 2012), we consider the nexus as a construct adept to SNS communication. The process involves multiple reconceptualisations of key terms of nexus theory: the notion of the object is reframed from material artefact to digital communication object; the notion of the artist is replaced by the notion of SNS user; the ability to act as social agents is ascribed to SNS messages rather than art objects; and, social action is understood as a process of distribution of agency that involves, primarily but not exclusively, SNS users and SNS messages.

Viewed from the perspective of nexus theory, SNS communication can be understood as a process of semiotic abduction (distribution) of agency. The process involves, firstly, human subjects active on SNS, i.e. (a) people who post, comment and react on social networks producing communicative objects such as messages and emoticon reactions (in a manner analogous to Gell's artist) in the role of agent, (b) who directly receive, consume and interpret such communicative objects, or who are indirectly involved with, benefit from, affect, or are affected from such SNS communications (in a manner analogous to Gell's recipient), in the role of patient. It involves, secondly, semiotic objects, including (a) recorded information in the form of social media expressions such as conversational texts, single messages (posts, comments, replies, tweets, etc.), media (images, videos, sound), hashtags, links etc. posted on social media, (b) meanings, either singular concepts or more complex propositional objects (propositions, syllogisms, narratives, etc.) assigned from expressions, or (c) sources and referents of these meanings, elicited either representationally (e.g. through a photograph or description), or non-representationally (e.g. by way of a proper name, connotation, allusion, or arbitrary sign); all three kinds of semiotic objects are capable of acting as index, and of attaining the position of either agent or patient according to the communicative operation in hand. In juxtaposition with Gell's material culture context, abduction of agency between human subjects and non-human objects in SNS communication produces effects on the symbolic, rather than material domain: it shapes beliefs and attitudes, cements existential presuppositions on what holds true, emboldens or undermines norms about what should be, and triggers affects, emotional reactions and evaluative thinking. The communicative nexus framed in the context of SNS communication involves, therefore, SNS users (in the place of artists), SNS expressions and meanings (as indexes), the original referent or source of such expressions or meanings

external to the SNS context (as prototypes), and other human subjects affected by or affecting the communication process (as recipients). An explicit mapping of this understanding of the nexus vis-a-vis Gell's definition of the main 'terms' or entities constituting the art nexus demonstrates that the scheme holds remarkably well, the only substantive modification being a re-definition of indexes as semiotic expressions rather than the material entities of the original theory (Table 1).

Table 1. Communicative nexus vs. Gell's (1998: 27) art nexus

Art nexus entities	Communicative nexus entities
1. Indexes: material entities which motivate abductive inferences, cognitive interpretations, etc.	1. Indexes: semiotic expressions on social media which motivate abductive inferences, cognitive interpretations, etc.
2. Artists (or other 'originators'): to whom are ascribed, by abduction, causal responsibility for the existence and characteristics of the index	2. Authors: to whom are ascribed, by abduction, causal responsibility for the existence and characteristics of the index
3. Recipients: those in relation to whom, by abduction, indexes are considered to exert agency, or who exert agency via the index	3. Recipients: those in relation to whom, by abduction, indexes are considered to exert agency, or who exert agency via the index
4. Prototypes: entities held, by abduction, to be represented in the index, often by virtue of visual resemblance, but not necessarily	4. Prototypes: entities held, by abduction, to be represented in the index, often by virtue of visual resemblance, but not necessarily

Further considerations emerge from this reframing of SNS communication as a semiotic nexus. In conceiving a single SNS conversation as nexus, the author (as primary agent) produces a particular expression (e.g., a post, comment, hyperlink, image or video, emoticon reaction) as index, which (becoming a secondary agent) has effects on the beliefs, norms and affects of SNS members involved (as patients) in the SNS communication process. Being a secondary yet efficacious agent, an SNS expression may also trigger further communicative action in the form of discussion (flow of comments, emoticons, shares, etc.), besides its effects on beliefs and

affects of other users. In doing so, the expression may acquire agency from the extra-semiotic prototypes which it refers to: historical events, biographies of people, and other similar referents. And, in addition, an SNS expression as index is involved in reciprocal abduction of agency with entities identified as recipients in the sense of Gell's theory of the nexus, i.e., subjects which it is indirectly affected by: for example, some institutional actor that promotes a certain authorised discourse or meaning propagated by the expression, or those which it indirectly affects, e.g., broader public opinion.

Building on the conceptualisation of SNS communication as a process of translation between semiospheres, we now turn to a potential integration with communicative nexus theory. In this context, authors and recipients can be understood as affiliated with particular multiple semiospheres. Indexes are to be understood as texts or signs. Prototypes define aspects of the semiospheres with which authors and recipients are affiliated. Partly due to the asynchronous nature of SNS communication, the process of translation produces a moment of liminality in terms of abduction of agency in the communicative nexus: at the moment of posting to SNS, the index accrues agency from its author, and through the author, from the beliefs and affects connected with the author's semiospheres, but the agency of the author (related to the posting artist) is undermined. Further to that, in the process of translation developing at the intermediate state between two semiospheres, the index now assumes the role of patient and offers itself as an "open signifier" to a reader, now elevated to the role of agent and endowed with agency to imbue new meanings into the index through abduction of agency from both the original author's meanings and the prototype structures (beliefs and affects) of the reader's semiosphere. It thus enacts a process of creolisation between these intersecting semiospheres.

An additional issue concerns the efficacy of the process of semiotic abduction of agency. If the index works as a trigger, it initiates the abduction of agency by activating, or "awakening", semiospheric structures of patients understood as prototypes: structures such as metaphors, narratives, personal experiences, family histories, post-memories, and accepted perceptions of contemporary political or cultural realities. The extent to which such semiospheric structures are activated is evidence of the efficacy of abduction of agency in the SNS context. Higher intensity of agency enables abduction of agency involving a larger number of recipients, who may belong to a more diverse range of semiospheres (communities sharing specific prototypes, including presuppositions, norms, narratives, and ways of communicating), and the

propagation of new instances of abduction, leading to a higher level of interaction in SNS conversation. In the process of SNS conversation, patients of earlier interactions become agents when starting to produce and share “their own” indexes in the form of comments, replies and reactions, or even through spawning out new conversations, representing prototypes (presuppositions, narratives, etc.) drawn from the semiospheres with which they are affiliated.

A further issue concerns the effect of structures of translation and abduction of agency on the monologic or dialogic nature of SNS communication: a consequential question, in the context of critique of digital participation (e.g., Carpentier 2015). As noted, an SNS conversation remain active as long as its participants continue serving as semiotic agents to stimulate discussion, with actual effect on the propensity of other participants to become active too, i.e., their semiotic agency. In an abstract model, an SNS conversation could be endless, but in practice it adheres to a “cost-benefit” principle: the conversation remains active as long as it is more beneficial for a participant to be active, i.e. to continue serving as an agent, or being mobilised by prior semiotic activity to shift from a positionality of patient to one of agent. But an SNS conversation viewed as communicative nexus could take the form of either (a) a dialogic situation, leading to the rise of processes of semiotic translation and creolisation, or (b) a non-dialogic situation, imprisoning participants within particular, bounded semiospheric “bubbles”, or “echo chambers”.

This theorisation suggests that the index works in the context of SNS conversations not only, or even predominantly, because it relates to the past on account of abduction of agency from author to index, or from prototype to index, but because it has agency in the present on account of abduction of agency from the target semiosphere’s prototype to the index). It thus privileges the affiliative identities of participants of the conversation beyond the original author, and their incorporation within particular semiospheres. It is important, of course, to note that the same person could be a member of more than one semiospheres, assuming different roles and identities within each semiosphere: as Gell notes, “the concept of agency [...] is relational and context-dependent, not classificatory and context free” (1998: 22). In our theorisation of SNS as communicative nexus, semiotic agency can be adduced not only to (human) authors and recipients, but also to indexes and (human or non-human) prototypes, as these four kinds of entities assume roles of agent and patient in different episodes of an SNS conversation. Semiotic

translation between semiospheres of SNS users is materialised through multiple abductions of agency involving binary combinations of index, author, recipient and prototype.

In the Delfi.lt conversation about the removal of Petras Cvirka's monument, we recognise the full repertoire of cases of abduction of agency (cf. Gell 1998: 29, Table 1), enabling a rich process of semiotic translation between multiple intersecting semiospheres. Any of the four kinds of communicative nexus entries - an Author, an Index, a Prototype of even a Recipient - can initiate a process of semiotic abduction of agency affecting any other entity. To offer an example, to provide background for the decision to remove the monument, the online article of delfi.lt linked in the initial post starting off the conversation, reports that vice-mayor of Vilnius "V. Benkunskas reminded that the council, in approving the removal of the monument, relied on the explanation provided two years ago by the Lithuanian Genocide and Resistance Research Center that P. Cvirka collaborated with the Soviet authorities and contributed to the repression of other writers of that time". In the originating process of abduction underlying this semiotic act, the role of the *agent* is assumed by the Genocide and Resistance Center (a Recipient in terms of nexus theory) whose written opinion semiotically imbues the vice-mayor (an Author, in the context of the passage) as *patient* in a process of the form Recipient-A → Author-P; but significantly, the Center also transfers agency to a perception or idea (a Prototype in the structural position of *patient*) typifying Cvirka as a collaborator of the Soviet regime, in a process of the form Recipient-A → Prototype-P. The perception of Petras Cvirka as Soviet collaborator serves then as a further semiotic *agent* in cascading processes of abduction: Prototype-A → Agent-P when an Author becomes exposed to this perception and becomes the *agent* of another process of abduction, Agent-A → Index-P when writing a comment such as "[h]e was a complete minion of the Soviet government and red as a beetroot"; and the comment itself, an instance of Index, generates abduction of agency of the form Index-A → Recipient-P, it becomes a secondary agent affecting the perceptions of a smaller or larger group of people exposed to the message, some do whom become agents of further processes of abduction of the form Recipient-A → Recipient-P, affecting other users when they react with an emoticon, positive or negative, to the comment.

The example of the previous paragraph can be represented as a knowledge graph compliant with the ontology, using, for convenience, an abridged notation whereby all relationships between entities mediated by some Semiotic Activity are replaced by shortcuts involving related entities (Fig. 4).

Figure 4. Knowledge graph of an SNS interaction on the removal of Petras Cvirka’s monument illustrating recursive processes of abduction of agency (abridged notation with Activity nodes represented as arcs).

In the process of encoding / decoding across semiospheres, Semiotic Activity corresponds to the abduction of agency directed relationship (\rightarrow), and particular triples in the knowledge graph of the form (Person: author) - [Semiotic activity: produced] \rightarrow (Expression: SNS message) map onto particular agent-patient forms of abduction of agency. The graph illustrates well how SNS comments can reinforce beliefs which may originate and have effects outside the virtual realm and into physical reality. Thus, a communicative nexus approach allows conceptualising SNS interaction as a domain of social agency, providing a persuasive account of how this ability to act semiotically is not confined to human actors directly implicated in communicative activity (i.e., authors), but also other human actors - individual or collective - who may affect or be affected by such activity (i.e., recipients), and most notably also non-human entities, such as the texts and signs (i.e., indexes) and norms, attitudes and perceptions (i.e., prototypes).

Conclusion

In this study, we presented an account of the working mechanisms of social networks related to the construction (encoding), dissemination, and

reading (decoding) of messages. The application of nexus theory offers a useful framework for understanding SNS communication as social action enabled by a process of infinite semiosis as abduction of agency. On the other hand, the application of semiosphere theory as represented in a knowledge graph compliant with the ontology offers an understanding of how meaning-making works within different systems of belief, norms and existential presuppositions between participants in a blended communication context such as SNS.

To address RQ1, our study draws from Yuri Lotman's semiosphere theory to conceptualise the creation, sharing and consumption of messages on social network sites as a process of semiotic translation, whereby SNS messages (texts, photographs, videos, hyperlinks, etc.) are considered as signs operating at the boundaries between the semiosphere of its author and the semiosphere of its recipients. This explains how messages lend themselves to multiple interpretations on SNS, conditioned by semiotic conventions (codes) and accepted norms, perceptions, existential presuppositions, and authorised narratives (framing schemas) of semiospheric communities, which extend beyond the virtual domain to encompass the physical reality which people in SNS interaction inhabit.

To address RQ2, in our elaboration of communicative nexus drawing from Alfred Gell's theory we established the circulation of agency between human and non-human (objectual) entities involved in this semiotic process of semiospheric translation - users who write and read messages, the messages themselves, the entities in the world which these messages refer to, and others who affect or are indirectly affected by the process. In the situated context of a particular interaction, Authors (active SNS users), Indexes (messages, texts), Prototypes (semiospheric schemas) and Recipients (affecting and affected actors) assume positional roles of agent and patient to initiate nested processes of abduction (circulation) of semiotic agency between them in almost any permutation: an author may draw agency from norms, perceptions or presuppositions shared within her semiosphere, and then transfer that agency to an SNS message, which then can autonomously assume the agency of changing the perceptions of its readers; but any reader assumes the position of patient not only in relation to a message, but also in relation to the semiotic code, norms, perceptions and presuppositions of the semiosphere in which the reader belongs, a prototype acting as a filter which blocks specific interpretations of the message which are unacceptable in the context of the semiosphere. The abduction of agency mirrors a translation process which is crucial in creating creolised spaces in which one community interacts with another; yet this mechanism can account equally for situations where SNS

interaction results in creolisation between participating semiospheric communities, and in those where the abduction of agency from sharply different semiospheric prototypes renders the possibility of semiotic translation impossible.

To address RQ3, we examined how an agency-oriented formal ontology of SNS semiotic activity on social network sites (Kirtiklis et al., forthcoming) can be a suitable foundation for the formal representation of semiotic translation and abduction of agency processes, both at the theoretical and at the empirical level. We established that it is possible to represent fruitfully important dimensions of SNS communication viewed as a semiospheric activity of translation using a knowledge graph compliant with the ontology. We also found that the ontology provides the expressive mechanisms to represent pairwise operations of distribution of agency between human actors and non-human objects, by mapping the agency abduction relationship such as Author-A \rightarrow Index-P as a more expressive structure of the form (Person: author) - [writes] \rightarrow (Message: post). Using a Facebook conversation on a contested issue of cultural memory and activism as a case study, we demonstrated how processes of communication between different semiospheres can be fully documented to account for the salience of opposed shared assumptions and semiotic codes of participants, and also how a recursive process of abduction of agency involving not only SNS users but also “real world” actors influencing and being influenced by SNS interaction, as well as SNS messages themselves, and the norms and assumptions of interacting semiospheric communities, can be formally represented.

As the ontology is activity-centric, aiming to make processes underlying SNS communication and its effects explicit, it provides a richer representation of entities in the two theoretical frameworks this study seeks to integrate: semiosphere is not represented as a single entity, but as a structure comprising the relationship between Persons (members of a semiosphere), a Collectivity (the semiosphere understood as an aggregate of semiotic actors), a Semiotic Code (the ‘language’ and mode of communication shared by the aggregate of semiosphere members), and a set of Meanings (associated with shared knowledge, presuppositions, affects, norms, etc.). The notion of the communicative nexus encompasses the full structure of entities and relationships provided by the ontology, in the context of a group of connected instances that are coherent within a given practice. Both authors (the equivalent of Gell’s artists) and recipients can be represented as Persons and, in the case of recipients, alternatively as Collectivities. An index can be represented by a structure

consisting of a Message and its activity-mediated relationships with Meanings and Concepts, privileging a representation that avoids an essentialist understanding of semiotic meaning. A prototype can be represented, simply, by correspondence to the Referent entity, but, in a more rigorously theorised manner, as an aspect of a semiosphere related to the Meanings which the Collectivity related to the semiosphere has belief or has affect for, and any associated Referents to these Meanings. Abduction of agency between pairs of nexus entities (Index, Author, Prototype and Recipient) are directly represented as relationships between particular entities in the ontology.

By addressing the semiotic mechanism of SNS communication in a way that takes into account the diversity of perceptions, presuppositions and norms between SNS users, the processes of translation involving users, communities of understanding they belong to, messages they create and consume, and the referents of those messages, as well as the abduction of agency between human and non-human entities involved in SNS interaction, we hope to contribute to better understand yet unexplored aspects of the semiotic mechanism of communication in blended social networks in a wider sense. Bridging this gap of understanding fosters better collaboration between different groups of society, engenders community empowerment and resilience in facing the challenges of the network society, and draws the lines to a higher level of social cohesion. In future work, we aim to apply this theorisation of semiotic activity on social network sites through the lens of our elaboration of semiosphere and communicative nexus theories, and its operationalisation in the form of the domain ontology discussed in this study, to empirically analyse and understand the often complex and dissonant interactions of social media users around questions of heritage, identity, and the difficult past.

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